

**ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MANAGEMENT IN
INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES**

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Abstract. *Effective management in industrial enterprises is crucial for their success and sustainability. It plays a pivotal role in achieving organizational goals, enhancing productivity, and ensuring competitiveness in the market. This article explores the key elements of effectively managing the industrial enterprises in our dynamic world.*

Key words: *effective management, economic growth, technological development, sustainability, competitive advantage.*

Abstrakt. *Samarali boshqaruv sanoat korxonalarining muvaffaqiyati hamda barqarorligi uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. U tashkiliy maqsadlarga erishish, samaradorlikni oshirish va bozorda raqobatbardoshlikni ta'minlashda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. Ushbu maqola jahonning dinamik sharoitida sanoat korxonalarini samarali boshqarishning asosiy elementlarini o'rganadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *samarali boshqaruv, iqtisodiy taraqqiyot, texnologik rivojlanish, barqarorlik, raqobatbardoshlik.*

Абстракт. *Эффективное управление на промышленных предприятиях имеет решающее значение для их успеха и устойчивости. Эффективное управление играет ключевую роль в достижении организационных целей, повышении производительности и обеспечении конкурентоспособности на рынке. В данной статье исследуются ключевые элементы эффективного управления промышленными предприятиями в нашем динамичном мире.*

Ключевые слова: *эффективный менеджмент, экономический рост, технологическое развитие, устойчивость, конкурентоспособность.*

In the dynamic and competitive global market, effective management of industrial enterprises is paramount to their survival and long-term success. It is not merely a set of isolated actions but rather a comprehensive approach that encompasses strategic planning, operational excellence, human capital management, technological innovation, financial management, sustainability, customer focus, continuous improvement, data-driven decision-making, and risk management.

Effective management of an organization is a complex, universal concept. In modern management, there is no generally accepted definition of it, and the boundaries of its qualitative content have not been established. According to

Professor O.S. Vikhansky, effective management can be judged by whether the organization works effectively or ineffectively [2].

If an organization wins in competition, then it is an efficiently operating enterprise; if it loses to competitors, it is an ineffective organization. In practice, the effectiveness of the management system is judged by the achieved performance results.

The main scientific hypothesis underlying the substantiation of the proposed concept for the development of effective management is the position that it is the mastery of intra-production management of the three main methods of effective management - strategic management, controlling as an integrated methodological and instrumental basis for supporting the main functions of management and a system of organizational training based on “cultivation” from domestic enterprises of self-learning organizations, based on their close interdependence, will be the foundation for the development of effective management in enterprises. According to the hypothesis, the model of effective management of any modern organization should be determined, first of all, by such priority factors of management effectiveness as: focus on the social aspects of a “learning” organization associated with the full disclosure of the intellectual potential of the organization’s personnel, encouraging the processes of self-organization and creativity in the team; flexibility of the internal mechanisms of the organization’s management systems and its compliance with the adopted strategy; adaptability and “responsiveness” to constant changes in the external environment.

Each option of the management system corresponds to a certain value of the efficiency criterion, and the task of optimal management is to find and implement a management option in which the corresponding criterion takes on the most favorable value.

Consequently, in relation to the managed system, there is a group of criteria that can be determined in accordance with the goals determined by economic policy in a specific period of time, and the specific operating conditions of a given enterprise or industry.

Thus, increasing the efficiency of the production management system involves finding the best organizational forms, methods, technology for managing a specific object in order to achieve certain technical and economic results by the managed system in accordance with a given criterion or system [3].

Effective management of industrial enterprises involves a combination of strategic planning, efficient operations, and skilled leadership. Here are some key methods for managing industrial enterprises effectively:

1. **Strategic Decision-Making.** Management is responsible for making strategic decisions that align with the organization's goals and objectives. This involves planning for the future, setting priorities, and allocating resources efficiently.

2. **Resource Optimization.** Efficient management ensures the optimal utilization of resources, including human capital, technology, and finances. This maximizes productivity and minimizes waste, contributing to cost-effectiveness.

3. **Operational Efficiency.** Management establishes and monitors processes to ensure smooth operations. This includes streamlining workflows, implementing quality control measures, and adopting best practices to enhance overall efficiency.

4. **Adaptability to Change.** Industrial enterprises operate in dynamic environments where change is constant. Effective management enables organizations to adapt to market fluctuations, technological advancements, and regulatory changes, ensuring long-term viability.

5. **Innovation and Technology Integration.** Successful management encourages innovation and the integration of new technologies. This fosters competitiveness by allowing enterprises to stay ahead of industry trends and respond to evolving customer needs.

6. **Risk Management.** Effective management involves identifying and mitigating risks that could impact the enterprise. This includes financial risks, market risks, and operational risks. A well-managed enterprise is better equipped to navigate uncertainties.

It should be noted that the considering of each method is targeted at reducing waste and eliminating the cost of operations [5], but taking them separately, the dual nature of waste, the result can vary immediately in each industrial enterprise depending on the area of the economy and the quality of the technology. In case of separate use, there is a chance of providing a short positive result – a decreasing in not productive waste.

By integrating these methods, industrial enterprises can enhance their overall performance, adapt to changes in the business environment, and achieve sustainable growth.

Conclusion.

By adopting a holistic approach to effective industrial enterprise management, companies can achieve sustainable growth, maintain a competitive advantage, and contribute to the overall economic prosperity. By aligning their strategic direction, optimizing operations, empowering their workforce, embracing innovation, managing finances responsibly, prioritizing sustainability, focusing on customers, fostering continuous improvement, leveraging data insights, and effectively managing risks, industrial enterprises can navigate the challenges of the modern market and secure a bright future.

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